

Evaluation of In-Vitro Anthelmintic and Thrombolytic Activities of Ethanolic Extract of *Asteracantha longifolia* Seed

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Abstract

Asteracantha longifolia has huge medicinal value in ancient Indian medical system. In the present investigation focused on extraction of phytochemicals from seeds by using ethanol menstruum. Ethanolic extract was subjected to identification tests for various phytochemicals, it is confirmed from the results presence of alkaloids, Carbohydrates, Glycosides, tannins, Flavanoids, proteins, Phytosterols and Triterpenoids in extract. Seed extract of *Asteracantha longifolia* were evaluated for anthelmintic and thrombolytic activities using an in-vitro models by taking Albendazole and EDTA as standard drugs respectively. In the anthelmintic activity by observing the paralysis time and death time of earthworms, it was disclosed that extract with concentration of 100mg/mL showed significant effect on earthworms. Thrombolytic activity studied on human blood samples, the results revealed that significant activity produced by the extract with concentration 30mg/mL. The study concluded that the ethanolic extract of seed showed significant Anthelmintic and Thrombolytic activities in a dose dependant manner.

Key words: *Asteracantha longifolia*, Ethanolic extract, Phytochemical screening, Anthelmintic activity, Thrombolytic activity.

1. Introduction

Nature has provided a complete storehouse of remedies to cure all ailments of mankind and its related diseases [1]. It as gifted us plenty of herbs and plants which contain bioactive substances like tannins, alkaloids, carbohydrates, terpenoids, steroids and flavonoids which provide definite physiological action on the human body. Herbal treatment is still used for many health problems. Herbs are safe, less toxic, economical and a reliable key natural resource of drugs all over the world [2].

Helminth is derived from the Greek word "helminths" meaning, intestinal worm. Helminth is a broad categorical term referring to various types of parasitic worms that reside in the body. The World Health Organization reveals that over two billion people are suffering from parasitic worm infections. It is estimated that by the year 2025, about 57% of the population in developing countries will be influenced. Helminthic infections are very common in men. Helminthic infections can serve as a threat to human beings, especially in developing countries. It leads to malnutrition [3], anemia [4] and pneumonia. Majority of the infections, which are due to worms are mostly limited to tropical regions [5]. For control of helminthic disease in different part of world are uses synthetic medicines which are very effective in curing helminthiasis, but it's also causes a number of side effects. The continued uses of synthetic anthelmintic/larvicidal drugs are also causing a major drug resistance problem in several parasitic diseases [6].

Thrombosis is the condition of blood clot formation inside a vein or artery vessel that blocks the blood flow. If it slips from the vessel wall, it could obstruct in the organs causing heart and vascular diseases such as ischemic heart disease and cerebrovascular disease. A blood clot forms when there is an imbalance in the blood coagulation system, leading to several serious health conditions, for instance, venous thromboembolism which can cause deep vein thrombosis and/ or pulmonary

embolism. The treatment for blood clot embolism involves antiplatelet, Thrombolytic, or thrombolytic medications. Thrombolytics, heparin, and warfarin are the main medications given for the prevention of blood clotting, whereas thrombolytic agents such as streptokinase dissolve the clot clinical practices [7]. Present Thrombolytics comprise the harmful life-threatening side effects. Limitations of existing Thrombolytic and cost effectiveness have prompted scientist and biochemist to go for alternate novel agent from natural sources [8].

Hygrophila auriculata belonging to family Acanthaceae; is also known as *Asteracantha longifolia*. The common plant growing in marshy and water logged areas. *Asteracantha longifolia* is described in ayurvedic literature as Ikshura, Ikshugandha and Kokilasha “having eyes like the Kokila or Indian Cuckoo”. *Asteracantha longifolia* is a plant common in India. Internally, the plant is used in vast range of diseases. The plant contains various groups of phytoconstituents, namely, phytosterols, fatty acids, minerals, polyphenols, proanthocyanins, mucilage, alkaloids, enzymes, amino acids, carbohydrates, hydrocarbons, flavonoids, terpenoids, vitamins, and glycoside [9]. The parts of this plant are widely used in traditional medicine for the treatment of various disorders, which include anasarca, diseases of the urinogenital tract, dropsy from chronic Bright's disease, hyperdipsia, vesical calculi, flatulence, diarrhea, dysentery, leukorrhea, gonorrhoea, asthma, blood diseases, gastric diseases, inflammation, cancer, rheumatism, painful micturition, menorrhagea [10-12]. Based on the medicinal properties of *Asteracantha longifolia* the present investigation was taken up with an objective to evaluate the invitro Thrombolytic activity and Anti helmenthic activity.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Collection and authentication of plant

During Oct-Nov 2021 the Sample of *Asteracantha longifolia* seeds were collected from surroundings of tirupathi, Andhra Pradesh, India. Taxonomically identified plant material was authenticated by Dr.Madhava Chetty, Associate Professor, Department of Botany, Sri Venkateswara University, Tirupathi.

2.2. Chemicals and reagents

All chemicals, reagents and solvents used were analytical graded and procured from, Merck and S.D Fine, HiMedia chemicals limited. Standard drug Albendazole oral suspension-200mg/5mL were purchased from Apollopharmacy, Ananthapuramu, A.P., India.

2.3. Preparation of plant extract

Asteracantha longifolia seeds were completely dried and powdered to get effectual process of extraction. The powdered sample was soaked in ethanol solvent at seed material to solvent ratio 1:3 w/v. The mixture was kept aside for 72 hrs at room temperature with frequent manual agitation and closed with aluminum foil. The extract obtained were filtered, evaporated using rotary evaporator. Resulted solid was dried and stored in sterile desiccators until further analysis.

2.4. Preliminary phytochemical screening

The ethanolic extract of *Asteracantha longifolia* was tested for phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, alkaloids, triterpenes, sterols, amino acids and fatty acids using standard phytochemical methods [13-15].

2.5. In-vitro Antihelminthic activity of *Asteracantha longifolia* seed extract

2.5.1. Collection of worms: The earth worms belonging to species *Pheritima posthuma* (annelida), about 3-6 cm in length and 0.1-0.2 cm in width, weighing about 0.8-0.34g, were collected from the moist soil of Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University, Ananthapuramu, Andhra Pradesh, India.

2.5.2. Preparation of samples of seed extract and Standard drug: Different concentrations (10mg/mL, 50mg/mL, 100mg/mL) of *Asteracantha longifolia* seed extract were prepared by using 0.5% w/v of CMC as a suspending agent and the final volume of each was made up to 25mL. Standard Albendazole drug (20mg/mL) was prepared just like extract samples with 0.5% w/v of CMC.

2.5.3. Procedure for Anthelmintic activity: The anthelmintic activity was performed on adult indian earthworm *Pheretima posthuma*. Three different concentrations (10 & 50 & 100 mg/mL) of ethanolic extract of *Astercantha longifolia* seed and standard suspensions were taken in petridishes. The earth worms divided into 5 groups of two worms in each petridish and observed for paralysis or death [16]. Mean time for paralysis was noted when no movement of any sort could be observed, except when the worm was shaken vigorously. The time death of worm (min) was recorded after ascertaining that worms neither moved when shaken nor when given external stimuli. The test results were compared with control and reference drug Albendazole (20 mg/mL) treated samples.

2.6. In-vitro Thrombolytic activity of *Astercantha longifolia* seed extract

2.6.1. Preparation of 0.25M calcium chloride (CaCl₂): 6.9375g of calcium chloride (CaCl₂) was dissolved in 250 mL of distilled water to get 0.25M of calcium chloride (CaCl₂). Calcium chloride plays a major role in activation of platelets, which then clotting takes place and promotes thrombosis process.

2.6.2. Preparation of plasma preparation: Blood sample was collected from a healthy volunteer about 20-25 years old and to prevent the blood clotting process collected sample placed in EDTA tubes. Then the tubes subjected to centrifugation process with 2000 rpm speed for 20 min to separate blood cell content from plasma.

2.6.3. Procedure for Thrombolytic activity: 0.1 mL of ethanolic extract in various concentration, 0.2 mL of plasma and previously prepared calcium chloride solution were taken in fusion tubes. Then the test sample tubes were incubated at 37°C on a waterbath. EDTA and sodium citrate were taken to compare the efficacy of the extract. The clotting time also called prothrombin time [17], it was noted by checking the fusion tube for every 10 seconds.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Preliminary phytochemicals

Identification tests for Phytochemicals disclosed that the ingested ethanolic extract contains alkaloids, Carbohydrates, Glycosides, tannins, Flavanoids, proteins, Phytosterols and Triterpenoids.

Table No.1: Phytochemical Screening of Ethanolic extract of *Astercantha longifolia* seed

S.No	Chemical constituents	Observation
1.	Alkaloids	Present
2.	Carbohydrates	Present
3.	Glycosides	Present
4.	Saponins	Absent
5.	Phenols	Absent
6.	Tannins	Present
7.	Flavanoids	Present
8.	Phytosterols	Present
9.	Proteins	Present
10.	Amino acids	Present
11.	Diterpenoids	Present
12.	Anthraquinones	Absent

3.2. Anthelmintic and Thrombolytic activity

The anthelmintic activity of ethanolic *A. Longifolia* seed extract was determined in-vitro using earthworms and standard albendazole anthelmintic drug. Ethanolic extract in 0.5% w/v CMC were used to determine anthelmintic activity and showed the effect in a dose dependant manner. The Results of anthelmintic activity were depicted in the Table.2, disclosed that different

concentration of extracts has exhibited significant paralysis and death time of earthworms as compared with Albendazole reference drug. Ethanolic extract with concentration 100mg/mL has taken less time to cause desired effects on worms. Standard drug (20mg/mL) and extract with concentration 100mg/mL has taken 42.185 ± 3.2 and 44.45 ± 3.5 paralysis time respectively, similarly standard and extract (100mg/mL) have a close time of Death.

Thrombolytic activity of extract was compared with EDTA. Results obtained from the experiments were showed in the Table.3, revealed that activity produced in a dose dependant manner. Ethanolic extract of 30mg/mL showed a significant Thrombolytic activity, it was taken 6.58 ± 1.1 min of coagulation time.

Table.2: Anthelmintic potency of Ethanolic Extract of *Asteracantha Longifolia seed*

Compound	Concentration (mg/mL)-25mL	Time (min) X±S.D	
		Paralysis(P)	Death(D)
Standrad Albendazole	20mg/mL	42.185 ± 3.2	91.86 ± 2.4
EEAL	25mg/mL	62.33 ± 2.1	137.5 ± 1.3
	50mg/mL	58.275 ± 2.2	120.9 ± 1.3
	100mg/mL	44.45 ± 3.5	92.845 ± 3.2

EEAL- Ethanolic Extract of *Asteracantha Longifolia seed*

Table.3: Thrombolytic activity of Ethanolic Extract of *Asteracantha Longifolia seed*

Compound	Concentration	Amount of plasma	Amount of Extract	CaCl ₂ solution	Time of coagulation(min) X±S.D
EEAL	10mg/mL	0.2mL	0.1mL	0.3mL	2.45 ± 0.5
	20mg/mL	0.2mL	0.1mL	0.3mL	3.1 ± 0.7
	30mg/mL	0.2mL	0.1mL	0.3mL	6.58 ± 1.1
Standard EDTA	20mg/mL	0.2mL	0.1mL	0.3mL	7.59 ± 1.0

4. Conclusion

The present study concludes that the ethanolic extract of *Asteracantha longifolia* seed exhibited significant anthelmintic activity and Thrombolytic activity as compared with standard drugs. Further investigation using *in-vivo* methods are recommended to estimate the efficacy of *Asteracantha longifolia* seed extract and to exploring the active constituents which are responsible for the anthelmintic and Thrombolytic activities of *Asteracantha longifolia* seed extract.

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Conflict of interest

The author's declared that they have no conflict of interest.

References

1. W. M. Kone, K. K. Atindehou, T. Dossahoua, and B. Betschart, "Anthelmintic Activity of Medicinal Plants Used in Northern Côte d'Ivoire Against Intestinal Helminthiasis", *Pharmaceutical Biology*, Vol. 43(1), pp. 72–78, 2005.

2. S.M.M. Rahman, M. Islam, Md.R. Haque, Md.I. Hossain, Md. Atikullah, K. Ahammed, A. Islam, S.M. Jui, and Md.O. Faruk, "Cytotoxic and Anthelmintic Activity of Three Selected Medicinal Plants Used in Bangladesh", *Int. J. Pharm. Sci. Rev. Res.*, 55(1), pp.114-119, 2019.
3. (2019) The ManilaMed website. [Online]. Available <https://www.manilamed.com.ph>
4. H. Chergui, M. Akhoundi, R. Benamouzig, and A. Izri, "Severe iron deficiency anaemia due to hookworm infection diagnosed by capsule endoscopy", *International Journal of Infectious Disease*, Vol.104, pp.271-272, March.2021.
5. S.N. Mathias, E.H. Mshelia, B.B. Danbala, and A.A. Biambo "In Vitro Anthelmintic Activity of Leaf Extracts of *Celosia laxa* Schum.&Thonn", *Open Journal of Applied Sciences*, Vol.11, 2021.
6. K. Sunita, P. Kumar, M.A. Khan, Sadaf, S.A Husain, and D. K. Singh, "Anthelmintic/larvicidal activity of some common medicinal plants", *European Journal of Biological Research*, Vol. 7 (4), pp. 324-336, 2017.
7. S. Sukati¹, K. Jarmkom, S. Techaoei, N. Wisidsri, and Warachate Khobjai, "In Vitro Anticoagulant And Antioxidant Activities Of Prasapalai Recipe And *Zingiber Cassumunar* Roxb. Extracts", *International Journal of Applied Pharmaceutics*, Vol 11(5), 2019.
8. Mohammed A., Yogananth N., Syed A.M., and Anuradha V., "Evaluation of *In vitro* anticoagulant and antimicrobial activities of *Gymnema sylvestre*" *International Journal of Advanced Research in Biological Sciences*, Vol. 4(7), 2017.
9. A.Doss, and S.P. Anand "Preliminary Phytochemical screening of *Asteracantha Longifolia* and *Pergularia daemia*", *World Applied Sciences Journal*, Vol. 18(2), pp. 233-235, 2012.
10. Tejashri, S. Hasabe, and A.R. Dhole, "A Potential Herbal Plant- *Asteracantha Longifolia*" *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science*, Vol. 3(3), March.2018.
11. A.S. Kumar, B.V.V. Sandeep kumar, D.Pavan Kumar, Y. Naresh, and A.Priyanka, "Analgesic activity of ethanolic extract of *Asteracantha Longifolia* seeds", *International Journal of Advances in Pharmacy and Nanotechnology*, Vol.1(2), pp. 56-59, 2011.
12. Madhavachetty K., Sivaji K., and Tulasi Rao K., Flowering plants of chittoor district, Students offset Printers, Tirupati, 2008.
13. K. Hemamalini, A. Rajani, U. Vasireddy, and E. Ratna sundari, "Anthelmintic activity of methanolic leaf extract of *sophora interrupta*", *Int. Res. J. Pharm.*, Vol.4 (8), pp.148-150, 2013.
14. Ishnava K.B., and Konar P.S., "In vitro anthelmintic activity and phytochemical characterization of *Corallocarpus epigaeus* (Rottler) Hook. f. tuber from ethyl acetate extracts", *Bull Natl Res Cent.*, Vol. 44(33), 2020.
15. D. Veerakumar, and M.Muthulingam, "Preliminary Phytochemical Analysis and Spectroscopic Analysis Methanolic Extract of *Asteracantha Longifolia*(Nees.)", *Journal of Pharmaceutical Research International*, Vol. 33(19B), pp.80-87,2021.
16. Anantha et al., invitro anti helmentic activity of aqueous and alcoholic extracts of aerva lanata seeds and leaves, *j. pharmaceutical sciences and research*, Vol. 2(5), pp. 317-321, 2010
17. Turner Ra, and Hebborn P, "Screening methods in Pharmacology", *Academic Press*, Vol.2, pp.210-245, 1971.